

FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE ONLINE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Today, education plays an important role in human life, because with its help, people can achieve incredible heights, become sought-after and professional specialists in their field. The slogan about the role of education in modern society sounds like this: "Education is for the development of self-confidence of a person, to help him achieve all his goals, as well as to have a bold and realistic point of view, to move forward. should serve as a basis". Education helps a person to open his potential, to learn new and modern knowledge, to become literate and moral. Therefore, continuous education is an important step in the spiritual growth of a person.

Online education is widely used in our modern age. In particular, in our country, all conditions are being gradually created for higher education and general schools to be able to use online educational platforms. In 2002, for the first time in the country, a video conference was organized between the Office of the President, the Ministry of Foreign Economic Relations, the University of World Economy and Diplomacy and the Tashkent State University of Economics. Among them, the use and participation in online video conferencing has become commonplace. Especially, in the system of higher education, using the opportunities of distance learning for the audience of students of Uzbekistan by professors and teachers of the world's leading higher education institutions on the basis of online lectures and master classes. warming up[1]. In addition to, public educational institutions, distance learning courses are organized in the network of

tutoring, and students study at home. The introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the educational process has led to the creation of a new form of distance learning - in addition to traditional teaching methods. In distance learning, the student and the teacher are in constant communication with each other through spatially separated learning courses, forms of control, electronic communication and other technologies of the Internet. Distance learning based on the use of Internet technology provides access to the global information education network, performing a number of important new functions based on the principles of integration and interaction. Distance learning provides an opportunity for all those who want to learn to continuously improve their skills. In such a teaching process, the student learns and monitors independent teaching materials in an interactive mode, conducts supervision under the indirect guidance of the teacher, and interacts with other “virtual learning group” students in the group. For obvious reasons, distance learning is not available for those who do not have the opportunity to study in full-time departments of educational institutions, for example, who do not require health care, who want to change their profession, or who want to improve their skills in adulthood. Teaching is a very convenient form of education. Interactive audio and video conferencing is designed to communicate with each other over a period of time, to send and receive e-mail feedback, that is, to send and receive messages[2].

Similar to attending a physical campus and learning in person, there are advantages and disadvantages of attending a [virtual classroom](#) and learning online. Among the many benefits of online learning, you’ll find that virtual education allows you to enjoy a more flexible schedule, can reduce the cost of your degree, and can allow you to more easily develop your career alongside furthering your education. While there are many pros to online learning, there are cons to consider. Staying on task and being self-motivated can be challenging in its own way; which is part of the reason why online learning isn’t right for everyone. By understanding more about the advantages and disadvantages of

online learning, you can get a better idea of whether it might be suitable for you and your educational and career goals. Among the many benefits of an online learning, you'll find virtual classrooms are great for people who are advancing their education while working. In a traditional classroom, lectures will be scheduled at a specific time of day and your schedule will be formed around the availability of classes. If you're currently employed and courses aren't available after your working hours, it can be difficult to juggle a course load in addition to your work duties. When attending a virtual campus, online learning allows for far more autonomy in deciding your own schedule. That means you can study whenever it's convenient for you. Live with some noisy roommates? Having more control over your schedule also means you can avoid distractions easier.

Education can be expensive, but virtual learning can provide a number of ways for students to save. Not having to commute to campus can help you save on transportation costs. Every year, the average student spends more than a thousand dollars on textbooks and course materials. Virtual coursework often takes advantage of virtual resources, which translates into less money spent on textbooks. Tuition costs can also vary between online and on-campus programs. For instance, at Drexel University, students enrolled in online programs in the School of Education receive a 25% discount off the price of regular tuition. Most online programs offered by the school are also financial aid eligible. Between all these sources of savings, cost-cutting can be an enormous benefit of online classes. Because your schedule isn't dictated by classes, you can spend more time doing the things you want. Plus, in addition to saving money, not having to commute also means saving time because you don't need to travel to-and-from campus. That extra time can be used in any way you want, such as focusing on your career or spending time with your family. All you need is a digital device and an internet connection, and you have access to the necessary tools to further your education and earn your degree on your own time.

Another reason why online school is better for some is the increased variety

of education options. Since students are not required to travel to campus for courses schedule on specific days and times, students can enroll in the courses they are most interested in. There's no need to rearrange schedules, students in an online program can take the course they want and complete the coursework at a time that is most convenient for them. Through online courses, students can gain the knowledge they need to earn their degree or grow in their profession. Online courses allow you to earn essentially the same range of different degrees that can be earned from a traditional educational environment. That includes learning certificates and professional certifications to master's degrees or doctoral degrees.

The Uzbek higher education system and its institutions were able to respond promptly to the situation caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. Since 2016, the national Higher Education Reform Experts (HEREs) team has contributed to an exploration of digital education approaches and helped to build capacity and develop a policy framework. As a result, during the academic year 2020–21, as the pandemic developed, remote learning in some educational institutions began to move online. The [Digital Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy](#) was announced in October 2020, with a focus on e-governance, digital education and infrastructure. The Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education prioritised the development of online courses and curricula, support for staff and students, professional development, data protection, and monitoring tools and techniques. Since the start of the Covid-19 pandemic, the national EDUUZ channel has been launched, with information about changes in the field of education and materials for independent learning . More than 3,500 electronic textbooks in various disciplines have been posted on the Innovation Library website. This shift was possible as a result of the experience already accumulated by universities well before the pandemic in the field of online pedagogy and methods of assessing learning outcomes, the acquisition of various digital tools, and their effective implementation. It was also possible due to a general strengthening of the potential of teachers and students, and of expert knowledge at system level[4].

The national HEREs team had already started to actively promote the topic of digitalisation in higher education. The process began with a [seminar on ICT-based learning in Petra, Jordan, on 26–27 October 2015](#), organised under the EU’s Support and Promotion of Higher Education Reform Experts (SPHERE) initiative. This was followed in November 2016 by the SPHERE technical assistance mission “Perspectives of E-learning and ICT-based education: applicability of best practices in Uzbek Higher Education Institutions”, in which more than 70 teachers and specialists participated. A number of additional technical assistance missions and regional workshops were conducted during the period 2017–2019 on topics such as academic libraries and information support for universities (March 2017); improving the quality of teaching in higher education institutions through new curricula and smart technologies or e-modules; e-learning, digital skills and open e-resources (September 2019); and digitalisation of the university, its concept and role in the reforming of higher education institutions (June 2021)[5].

To sum up, it should be noted that traditional learning methods allow the teacher to decide how they will convey information to their students, but online learning provides more flexibility and gives children control over their education. We all learn differently – some of us prefer quiet study, others like interactive tasks and being challenged under pressure. While there are tasks online, one of the advantages is that it gives students time to teach themselves concepts differently. Some students prefer to learn slowly and explore different learning methods, helping them fully retain information. Once they feel prepared, they can then take online tests or ask their parents to challenge them on what they have learnt.

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